

Co-creating social transformation:

*IN-HABIT methodology to transform
vulnerable urban realities from within*

UNIVERSIDAD
DE
CÓRDOBA

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement No 869227

Co-creating social transformation:

IN-HABIT methodology to transform vulnerable urban realities from within.

Methodological guide for the replication of the IN-HABIT methodology.

Authors:

María del Mar Delgado Serrano (Universidad de Córdoba) orcid.org/0000-0003-0171-6097

Francisco J. Martínez Carranza (Universidad de Córdoba) orcid.org/0009-0003-0871-5465

Catalina Cruz Piedrahita (Universidad de Córdoba) orcid.org/0000-0002-2737-1210

Nuria Chacón Molina (Asociación Vecinal Unión y Esperanza de las Palmeras) orcid.org/0009-0009-3663-6784

doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16985974

August 2025, Córdoba, Spain.

This document is part of the IN-HABIT project (Inclusive Health and Wellbeing in Small and Medium-Sized Cities), funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme (Grant Agreement No. 869227)..

TRANSFORMING URBAN WELLBEING STARTS LOCALLY

The IN-HABIT project (Inclusive Health and Wellbeing in Small and Medium-Sized Cities), funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 programme, has explored how inclusive, nature-based, and socially innovative interventions can transform vulnerable urban contexts. In Córdoba, Spain, a significant part of the work has focused on Las Palmeras, one of the country's most disadvantaged neighbourhoods. Over five years, residents, researchers, local authorities, and grassroots organisations **have worked together to imagine and co-create new forms of inclusive wellbeing.**

This methodological guide draws from that experience and **provides a practical roadmap to replicate and adapt the IN-HABIT approach in other neighbourhoods, cities, and with other vulnerable groups.** Through participatory processes and integrated solutions, both tangible and intangible, it shows that it is possible **to generate real, sustainable, and context-sensitive transformations.**

The guide is designed for local authorities, community associations, urban professionals, researchers, and social actors who aim to design and implement community-driven interventions that reduce inequalities and promote health and wellbeing in an inclusive way.

In these pages you will find:

- The key principles of the IN-HABIT methodology.
- The steps to follow, including tools and recommendations.
- Concrete examples of interventions.
- Success factors.
- Barriers and strategies for adaptation.

We invite you to explore this guide as a flexible and adaptable resource, which can be used as a whole or consulted in parts, depending on the needs of each context.

Access the video explaining the methodology at:

youtu.be/IJca-nrblwg

***The starting point:
context and methodological foundations***

Salud y Bienestar Inclusivos en Pequeñas y Medianas Ciudades

Este proyecto ha recibido financiación del fondo para la investigación y la innovación Horizonte 2020 de la Unión Europea bajo el acuerdo nº869227

UNIVERSIDAD
DE
CÓRDOBA

PAX
Potius de la Asunción

AYUNTAMIENTO DE CÓRDOBA

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

7

01. INTRODUCTION

10

02. CURRENT URBAN CHALLENGES

12

03. THE IN-HABIT PROJECT IN CÓRDOBA

18

04. METHODOLOGY

20

05. REPLICATING CÓRDOBA MODEL

50

06. METHODOLOGICAL ADAPTATION FRAMEWORK

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

01. INTRODUCTION

The continuous growth of the urban population is transforming cities worldwide (Carmichael et al., 2017). Although urbanisation brings economic and social benefits, it also has profound effects on health and wellbeing, intensifying segregation and existing inequalities (Badland & Pearce, 2019; Carmichael et al., 2017). In many cases, urban environments amplify these gaps, disproportionately exposing minorities and vulnerable populations to situations of risk.

Factors such as air pollution, noise, waste accumulation, extreme weather events, precarious employment, long commutes, or social isolation contribute to the deterioration of both physical and mental health, leading to a general decline in wellbeing (Kuddus et al., 2020). These impacts particularly affect people with low incomes, older adults, migrants, ethnic minorities, and individuals with disabilities, who often face multiple and interconnected barriers that limit their access to healthcare, decent housing, employment, green spaces, and social support networks (Corburn, 2017; Short et al., 2018).

In the face of this reality, it is increasingly important to address health and wellbeing from a cross-cutting and holistic perspective.

Cities are under strong pressure to reduce socio-economic inequalities and to guarantee equitable access to urban wellbeing. To achieve this, innovative approaches are needed that integrate **social justice, environmental sustainability, and community participation**. At the same time, contemporary research stresses the need to ground urban planning in scientific evidence and context-specific approaches (De Sá et al., 2022).

Within this framework, the IN-HABIT research project, funded by the Horizon 2020 programme, explores strategies to increase Inclusive Health and Wellbeing in small and medium-sized European cities. It examines how inclusive, nature-based, and socially innovative interventions can transform urban environments.

The project is being developed in four cities: Córdoba (Spain), Lucca (Italy), Riga (Latvia), and Nitra (Slovakia). Despite hosting a large share of the European urban population, small and medium-sized cities are often absent from policy and research priorities (McPhearson et al., 2016).

IN-HABIT addresses structural inequalities through the development of so-called **Visionary and Integrated Solutions (VIS)**. They are **integrated** because they combine intangible interventions, such as social, cultural, or participatory innovations, with tangible ones, such as infrastructure improvements, nature-based solutions, or digital and technological tools. They are **visionary** because they mobilise undervalued local resources such as culture, food systems, human-animal bonds, or the transformative potential of art and nature. Although each city focuses on different groups and strategies, they all share a common methodological framework and generate experiences that can be replicated in different urban contexts.

This document presents the strategy carried out in Córdoba, Spain, to address a central challenge: **improving inclusive health and wellbeing in vulnerable contexts through a participatory and context-sensitive approach**. It proposes replication guidelines based on the experience and lessons learned during the five years of IN-HABIT's implementation. The city has functioned as a **living laboratory of social innovation and research, co-creating** interventions designed to improve **inclusive health and wellbeing (IHW)** in urban contexts with high levels of vulnerability.

These guidelines describe the key processes and highlight both the success factors and the opportunities and barriers that arise in socially complex urban contexts, thus contributing to European objectives of **inclusion, innovation, and community resilience**. Their purpose is to serve as an example for designing interventions tailored to specific realities and to support institutions, professionals, and local actors interested in applying or adapting the approaches developed.

By transferring theoretical knowledge into applicable solutions, this document acts as a bridge between research and practice. IN-HABIT proposes a replicable model of inclusive urban transformation, showing how a medium-sized city like Córdoba can lead innovation in health and wellbeing, in line with the European Union's principles of sustainability, social cohesion, and territorial equity.

02. CURRENT URBAN CHALLENGES

Vulnerability is a persistent reality in many European cities. Factors such as structural inequality, economic precariousness, pressure on public services, and successive socio-economic and health crises have deteriorated living conditions in numerous cities and neighbourhoods.

In Spain alone, there are more than 600 vulnerable neighbourhoods. In these contexts, poverty and exclusion tend to concentrate geographically, limiting access to basic services, educational and employment opportunities, healthcare, and quality public spaces.

IN-HABIT's work in Córdoba has focused mainly on one of these vulnerable neighbourhoods, Las Palmeras, which is marked by strong social stigmatisation, structural dependence on public assistance, family breakdown, gender violence, lack of role models, and the failure of traditional educational models. It is also characterised by territorial segregation and disconnection between its residents and the rest of the city.

Problems such as illegal activities, neighbourhood conflicts, and police raids are frequent. In addition, the wellbeing of the population is limited by unemployment, the poor quality of social housing, economic instability, the lack of green areas and public spaces, low educational levels, and restricted access to culture.

Unhealthy lifestyles (including unbalanced diets, sedentary behaviour, obesity, early drug use, and unwanted pregnancies) further worsen the overall state of health. Cases of ethnic discrimination and social exclusion are also present, making being born in the neighbourhood itself a source of stigma.

In response to this reality, IN-HABIT has developed a strategy tailored to the local context, seeking to **address these challenges through the direct participation of the community**. Numerous social VIS (Visionary and Integrated Solutions) have been launched to engage residents, increase access to culture, strengthen the sense of belonging, and combat isolation.

Alongside the work carried out in Las Palmeras, the project has also addressed the situation of people experiencing **homelessness**, whose profile has changed significantly in recent decades. Homelessness is no longer linked only to a lack of income but has become an extreme expression of social exclusion. Today, a person may have income (from employment or benefits) yet still lack access to stable and decent housing.

Factors such as the breakdown of family networks, job loss, mental health issues, bureaucratic barriers, or the absence of strong local ties can all push someone into homelessness, even in cities with available public resources. This phenomenon, more complex and less visible than traditional poverty, requires interventions that go beyond temporary assistance.

IN-HABIT has implemented its methodology with homeless people to promote inclusive health and wellbeing, through nature-based solutions and cultural and training activities designed to encourage active participation, self-esteem, skills development, and the rebuilding of social networks.

03. THE IN-HABIT PROJECT IN CÓRDOBA

IN-HABIT proposes a **replicable methodology to promote inclusive health and wellbeing** in vulnerable urban contexts, starting from a participatory and place-based approach.

The model is built on inclusive, multi-actor governance, actively involving residents, local authorities, research teams, and social organisations, and recognising the essential role of so-called **local community activators** (LCA's), as key figures to connect the project with the community.

This approach strengthens institutional collaboration, allows actions to be adapted to real local needs, and reinforces the protagonism of participants, thereby increasing both the **impact** and the **sustainability** of interventions. It also helps to foster social cohesion, mobilise local resources, and develop collective capacities.

One of the central structures of the project has been the **IN-HUB**, an urban laboratory for social innovation and inclusive governance that functions as a space for coordination, dialogue, and decision-making.

In Córdoba, the IN-HUB has been made up of women residents of Las Palmeras, social organisations and NGOs, companies, public institutions, researchers, educators, and community activators.

This working space operates at different levels: it identifies needs and possible actions, drives strategic processes, defines local priorities, facilitates connections between institutional and community actors, and monitors actions. The IN-HUB has met regularly and has acted as a platform to ensure that proposed solutions are viable, contextualised, and shared by those living in the areas of intervention. Its **horizontal and flexible** logic has enabled the process to be sustained over time, adapt to new needs, and give value to previously underused resources.

Interventions have been developed through a combination of intangible and tangible actions (Visionary and Integrated Solutions – VIS), aimed at generating change from the bottom up. Before implementing tangible actions in Las Palmeras, IN-HABIT prioritised **recovering social fabric, making community assets visible, and involving residents** in collective improvement processes.

Among the **social and cultural** (also called soft) **VIS**, notable examples include traditional celebrations such as Christmas festivities, Carnival, and the May Crosses, video-dance activities, theatre plays based on women's stories from the neighbourhood, cultural cycles and concerts, videos produced by residents to showcase the neighbourhood in international competitions, visits to cultural events in the city, recycling workshops, and campaigns to promote healthy lifestyles.

These activities have helped to strengthen the sense of belonging and collective self-esteem, while also generating new dynamics of participation. In parallel, **hard VIS** have been implemented in **urban public space**, such as the refurbishment and renaturalisation of the central square as a meeting place, the creation of a picnic area and a corridor along the Cantarranas stream, the embellishment of patios, the planting of more than 300 trees and 800 shrubs to create areas for socialisation, and the participatory creation of a large-scale mural in a public space.

One of the most significant advances has been the consolidation of a **volunteer women's group ("Las Vecinas")**, working closely with the community activators.

This core group has fostered the participation of residents, especially women and young people, generating both tangible and intangible changes in the perception of the neighbourhood, in internal relations, and in existing support networks. These transformations have not only improved the physical environment through increased biodiversity, but have also driven a symbolic and social transformation of the area.

In parallel, the experience in the homeless shelter has allowed the IN-HABIT approach to be applied to a socially invisible collective. Here, interventions have focused on **creating safe, green, and therapeutic spaces** within the shelter. A cement and concrete courtyard has been transformed into a gardened space for socialisation, an urban vegetable plot and a therapeutic garden have been created, and training and cultural activities have been organised to strengthen self-esteem, personal skills, and social integration.

Far from being a mere assistance strategy, this work has emphasised the **direct participation** of homeless people in all stages of the process, from design to implementation, recognising their personal, social, and teamwork skills.

Both in Las Palmeras and in the homeless shelter, social and physical interventions have been designed, developed, and managed in a participatory way, reflecting the project's commitment to transformation that grows from within the communities themselves.

The experience in Córdoba shows that, through **contextualised methodologies and genuine co-creation processes**, it is possible to build sustainable and replicable alternatives to improve health and wellbeing in vulnerable neighbourhoods and among groups facing residential exclusion.

These processes, based on trust, listening, and active involvement, can open the way towards more just, resilient, and inclusive urban environments.

*IN-HABIT has carried out **more than 60 socio-cultural activities** in Las Palmeras over five years, with an estimated participation of **more than 1,500 people**. **Over 3,000 m² of public space** have been refurbished (including the community picnic area, the renovation of the central square, and the patios), **more than 300 trees and 800 brushes** have been planted, a **green, accessible, and sustainable corridor with innovative lighting** has been created, artistic spaces have been established, and **community training processes** have been launched in gardening, creative recycling, and health promotion.*

*At the homeless shelter, both tangible and intangible VIS have been combined, creating spaces for the development of social and interaction skills, encouraging teamwork and interpersonal relationships. Thanks to these efforts, more than 300 m² of green spaces have been created, including **an urban orchard and a therapeutic garden** that functions as a **space for rest, dialogue, biodiversity, and connection with nature**. In addition, another space has been rehabilitated by renaturalising and experimenting with the creation of a “patio of the future”, based on plants requiring minimal amounts of water. Some participants have begun processes of **personal autonomy** linked to the daily use of the space.*

Key lessons include the importance of ensuring **continuity** of community work beyond the duration of projects, the need to create **shared governance structures** that outlive institutional frameworks, and the **crucial role of art, culture, and nature** in driving inclusive health and wellbeing, even in highly vulnerable contexts.

Methodological guide to promote Inclusive Wellbeing in vulnerable contexts

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

04. METHODOLOGY

The methodological strategy of IN-HABIT redefines how urban transformations aimed at inclusive health and wellbeing can be conceived, implemented, and sustained, particularly among groups facing high levels of vulnerability. Far from applying standard solutions, the project proposes the following **paradigm shift**:

Cities are not merely recipients of policies, but active co-creators of change, capable of generating innovation and social inclusion by mobilising their own resources, knowledge, and contexts.

In this approach, **health and wellbeing** are understood as **collective, transversal, and dynamic processes**, resulting from the interaction between multiple social, economic, spatial, environmental, and cultural dimensions. **Participation** is therefore not a complement but the structural axis of intervention.

From the outset, **participatory tools** have been activated to understand the environment from within, such as mapping assets and vulnerabilities, neighbourhood workshops, collaborative diagnostics, and personal narratives.

These processes make it possible to design solutions and action plans that connect with the priorities expressed by the community. This principle is reflected in the **CO-CO-CO-CO approach** (co-design, co-implementation, co-management, and co-evaluation), which guides all phases of the project, from identifying needs to assessing results:

- **Co-design:** A collective process of identifying needs, generating ideas, and making decisions, encouraging dialogue between technical, institutional, and social actors, and recognising local knowledge as the foundation of design.
- **Co-implementation:** Residents and final beneficiaries participate actively in the execution of actions, which strengthens commitment, builds capacities, and ensures that interventions are adapted to the reality of the territory.
- **Co-management:** Promotes shared responsibility in the use, care, and maintenance of interventions, to guarantee their sustainability and local ownership, while reinforcing inclusive governance structures.
- **Co-evaluation:** Results are assessed collaboratively, combining quantitative, qualitative, and participatory tools, in order not only to measure impacts but also to learn, adjust, and improve continuously.

In Córdoba, this logic has been applied through a context-sensitive strategy that has considered issues such as institutional mistrust, territorial stigmatisation, and long-standing social exclusion.

Another key pillar of this methodology is the **creation of inclusive governance spaces**, such as the IN-HUB, conceived as a dynamic network that brings together residents, grassroots associations, public administrations, universities, and the private sector.

The IN-HUB operates as a horizontal and flexible working platform, ensuring that decisions remain connected to the reality of the territory. It works on several levels: identifying demands, validating proposals, promoting shared responsibility, and supporting implementation. Its open and evolving nature enables alliances to endure beyond the project, ensuring continuity of the processes set in motion.

The IN-HABIT methodological model is **adaptable, replicable, and scalable**. Its value does not lie in a fixed format, but in its guiding principles: a people-centred intervention, grounded in local knowledge, integrating multiple dimensions, and placing participation at the heart of innovation and sustainability. The results in Córdoba show that inclusive governance, combined with commitment, active listening, and genuine collaboration, can create more resilient, inclusive, and cohesive urban environments.

05. REPLICATING CÓRDOBA MODEL

The practical application of the IN-HABIT methodology in Córdoba has helped consolidate a structured process that can serve as a guide for other cities interested in initiating similar transformations. This intervention model rests on two essential pillars: on the one hand, **collaboration** between three key types of entities (the university, local authorities, and a grassroots association), and on the other, the central role of community activators, who connect the project's interventions with everyday reality.

The joint work between the university, public administrations, and the social fabric makes it possible to **integrate technical knowledge, political support, and territorial anchoring**. The university contributes tools for social transformation, analysis, monitoring, and systematisation of results. Local authorities ensure regulatory feasibility and institutional sustainability. The grassroots association acts as a bridge between the project and the community, offering closeness, legitimacy, and deep knowledge of the context.

Local community activators are a key figure for the success of the process. This role can be performed either by professionals with strong social involvement or by residents with the necessary training to combine technical skills with listening, empathy, and commitment.

Their work consists of energising the area, activating community networks, supporting interventions, and mediating between actors. Given the demands of the role, **it is recommended that it be a paid, stable, and full-time position**.

Building on this support structure, the model is organised into seven phases:

1. Understand the local context.

Preparation of a participatory diagnosis to identify vulnerabilities, existing assets, and needs expressed by the community. Tools include direct observation, interviews, social mapping, personal narratives, and meetings with key actors.

2. Identify and engage key actors.

Carry out an actor mapping exercise to identify individuals, groups, or organisations with the interest and capacity to make interventions possible. It is crucial to include less visible actors and to consider the most vulnerable members not only as beneficiaries but also as key agents in the process.

3. Build inclusive governance: the IN-HUB modelB.

Creation of a collaborative space between the public, private, academic, and community sectors, where decisions are taken in a horizontal and transparent way. The IN-HUB functions as a platform for the joint design, implementation, and evaluation of interventions.

4. Co-design an action plan.

Participatory design of interventions, combining intangible solutions (cultural, educational, or social activities) with tangible ones (improvements to public space, green infrastructure, facilities). The plan should be realistic, flexible, and consistent with the territory's resources and capacities, as well as with the project's scope of action.

5. Co-implement the actions.

Active participation of the community in the execution, maintenance, and monitoring of interventions. This involves training and capacity-building processes, with the aim of fostering social ownership and ensuring long-term sustainability.

6. Co-manage the results.

Engagement of the final beneficiaries in the maintenance and management of the interventions, to encourage their proper use and to strengthen involvement and shared responsibility.

7. Co-evaluation and monitoring.

Establishment of clear criteria and indicators on the objectives and desired impact, in order to evaluate progress and adapt actions if the expected outcomes are not achieved. Involving the community in this stage helps align project promoters' objectives with the needs expressed locally.

Another central element is **participatory evaluation**, understood not only as the measurement of impact but as an active part of the transformation process. The methodology combines quantitative and qualitative tools, such as surveys, direct observation, monitoring technologies, narrative records, and interviews. This makes it possible to capture both visible effects and more subtle changes in relationships, capacities, or perceptions. Moreover, evaluation is conceived as a **tool for collective learning**, guiding adjustments and reinforcing community ownership..

Preliminary analysis

1

Understand the local context

2

Identify and engage key actors

Governance and planning

3

Build inclusive governance: the IN-HUB model

4

Co-design an action plan

Co-implementation

5

Co-implement the actions

6

Co-manage the results

Follow-up and impact

7

Co-evaluation and monitoring

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

UNDERSTAND THE LOCAL CONTEXT

VULNERABILITY, RESOURCES AND PARTICIPATION

The first step of the methodology is to understand the local context and the cultural norms that shape community life. Before implementing any strategy in a vulnerable neighbourhood or working with groups at risk of exclusion, it is essential to carry out a detailed analysis of the situation of health and wellbeing, as well as an inventory of the existing services and infrastructures.

This diagnosis should also include the history of previous interventions, their outcomes, and, above all, a deep reflection on what has worked, what has not, and why.

In vulnerable areas, it is crucial to understand the emotional and political legacy of these interventions. Many communities have historically been neglected or misinterpreted, which generates scepticism and mistrust towards new initiatives. Building trust with residents, the project team, and community activators therefore requires time, presence, and consistency, but is absolutely essential.

This process should be led by people with genuine skills, experience, and commitment to addressing the social needs of the area, especially those responsible for decision-making and field coordination.

In this process, it is important to:

- Adopt an attitude of active listening rather than delivering speeches.
- Cross-check information to avoid bias.
- Remain open to different cultural and social perspectives.
- Identify key people to collaborate with and involve them from the outset..

Methods:

- Participant observation and individual conversations to uncover everyday realities and lived experiences that are often overlooked in formal data.
- Engagement with associations, businesses, and community groups to identify local goals, challenges, and power dynamics, and to understand the broader social landscape.
- Identification of key informants and respected voices to foster meaningful collaboration, while also recognising those who may support or hinder initiatives.

Critical success factors:

1. Involve professionals with technical expertise, knowledge of the local culture, experience in vulnerable contexts, and a strong commitment.
2. Use participatory tools to engage participants, paying particular attention to those traditionally excluded or overlooked.
3. Create synergies with existing institutions, organisations, and projects.
4. Take into account the history of previous interventions, including what has worked, what has not, and why.
5. Adapt working methods to local needs, habits, and cultures.
6. Identify and empower local actors and work with them.
7. Prioritise trust-building as a goal in itself.
8. Listen patiently and take time to compare and contrast different perspectives.
9. Allow local actors to set the pace and the language of engagement.

UNDERSTAND THE LOCAL CONTEXT

MAPPING OF VULNERABILITIES AND LOCAL RESOURCES

The mapping of vulnerabilities makes it possible to identify people who are most at risk (such as children, older adults, migrants, women, or persons with disabilities) and those who may be most affected, positively or negatively, by interventions. All of them should be considered key actors in the process.

This analysis should go beyond conventional indicators and address the structural causes of vulnerability, such as conflicts, geographical factors, stigmatisation, or systemic exclusion. To do so, it is recommended to apply an intersectional perspective, recognising that variables such as age, gender, ethnicity, legal status, income, or disability interact with one another, shaping both access to resources and the capacity of each person to participate.

At the same time, the process helps to detect underused assets that can be brought into value. Assessing resources and capacities allows a better understanding of what is available: from community infrastructures and human resources, to organisations already working in health and wellbeing.

It also helps identify significant gaps, such as the absence of health services, knowledge, adequate public spaces, training, or basic equipment. Furthermore, mapping can reveal leverage points: elements that already work and could be scaled up or connected to new initiatives.

Finally, it is essential to establish clear ethical guidelines that ensure approaches sensitive to gender, diversity, equity, and inclusion, avoiding any action that may unintentionally aggravate existing vulnerabilities.

Methods:

- Analytical frameworks that identify the intersection of variables present in inequality.
- Creation of safe spaces that foster trust, open dialogue, and the participation of traditionally excluded groups.
- Storytelling and interviews that provide personal perspectives, often absent from formal evaluations.
- Risk analysis to anticipate potential barriers.

Critical success factors:

1. Apply intersectionality frameworks to identify layers of exclusion.
2. Recognise informal leadership, local knowledge, and community rituals as assets.
3. Create spaces that encourage participation, trust, inclusion, and social cohesion.
4. Include both risks and strengths in the diagnosis.
5. Define ethical guidelines adapted to community dynamics.

UNDERSTAND THE LOCAL CONTEXT

PARTICIPATORY NEEDS ASSESSMENT

Interventions should be based on a participatory assessment of needs and priorities. The target group must be actively involved in identifying the needs related to inclusive health and wellbeing, as well as the most urgent problems within the area of action.

To achieve this, different tools can be used that capture not only what residents need, but also how they wish to participate in the process. This approach ensures that interventions are based on real demands rather than externally imposed ones. It also helps to uncover underlying social barriers, such as mistrust towards institutions, community fragmentation, or a sense of invisibility among certain minority groups.

At this stage, it is essential to communicate clearly and honestly the scope of the project, the resources available, and the expected outcomes, in order to avoid raising false expectations. It is also important that the project maintains enough flexibility to adapt to local demands and dynamics, avoiding rigid structures that might restrict participation or adaptability.

Methods:

- Community workshops and focus groups to foster collective reflection and co-creation, including voices that have traditionally been marginalised.
- Discourse analysis to reveal dominant narratives and power relations that shape perceptions and actions.
- Direct observation of public spaces to identify patterns of use, exclusion, and interaction, which provide valuable insights into underlying dynamics.

Critical success factors:

1. Work with open and flexible projects that can adapt to the needs of the target group.
2. Facilitate open participation formats, such as informal gatherings, outdoor activities, and peer-to-peer debates.
3. Plan for both immediate impact and long-term outcomes.
4. Treat identified needs as the result of a co-creative process.
5. Anticipate resistance or fatigue, and respond with empathy rather than pressure.

IDENTIFY AND ENGAGE KEY ACTORS

After understanding the local context, the next step is to identify and engage the actors who can influence the process or benefit from it. This means recognising not only the visible or most prominent institutions within the intervention area, but also the individuals and groups that usually remain in the background yet hold deep knowledge of the territory. Their involvement and collaboration are essential to build legitimacy, reduce resistance, and ensure that the project responds to real needs.

To achieve this, an actor mapping exercise is carried out, assessing not only their level of interest but also their influence and spheres of action. Some will play a central role in design and implementation, while others may only be involved in specific activities or prefer simply to be kept informed about progress.

An inclusive strategy recognises the most vulnerable groups not merely as passive recipients but as active agents in defining priorities and making decisions together with other social actors in their environment.

Actor mapping should not be conceived as a one-off or merely technical exercise, but as a political and social process subject to change. It must therefore be revised and updated continuously as new leadership emerges, alliances shift, or circumstances evolve.

Communication is a key element at this stage. In contexts marked by mistrust of institutions or by low levels of literacy and digital access, traditional channels may be insufficient. Accessible and creative formats are needed to reach the whole population: from clear and visually attractive leaflets distributed door-to-door to community radio programmes, participatory videos, or local social media. The goal is twofold: to inform, and at the same time to listen, recognise, and legitimise those who take part.

Methods:

- Dynamic actor mapping (interest, areas of action, influence, and interrelations).
- Interviews and door-to-door information to identify actors not immediately visible.
- Inclusive communication channels: newsletters and leaflets, radio programmes, social media, instant messaging, participatory videos, etc.
- Spaces for active listening and participatory dialogue.

Critical success factors:

1. Carry out and regularly update the actor map, adjusting it to changes and lessons learned.
2. Recognise and empower less visible actors and vulnerable groups.
3. Treat communication as a process of inclusion and legitimisation, not just information.
4. Avoid clientelist incentives, encouraging genuine and spontaneous motivation instead.
5. Build trust by aligning discourse and practice, maintaining a consistent presence in the territory.

BUILD INCLUSIVE GOVERNANCE

THE IN-HUB MODEL

The inclusive governance model of IN-HABIT is based on the creation of a Public-Private-People Partnership, known as the IN-HUB (Inclusive Hub). This structure functions as a social innovation laboratory, aimed at fostering genuine participation of stakeholders and aligning project goals with their needs.

More than a physical space, the IN-HUB acts as a meeting point and organisational platform that promotes cross-sector collaboration and facilitates the transformation process. Its design seeks to strengthen networks, promote structural dialogue, and ensure that decisions are guided by local perspectives.

The IN-HUB should integrate four key sectors:

- Residents, whose experiences and knowledge guide interventions.
- Public sector, providing regulatory, financial, organisational, and administrative support.
- Private sector, offering resources and facilitating the implementation of actions.
- Researchers and educational sector, contributing technical advice, monitoring and analysing results, providing scientific evidence and, in some cases, financial support.

This combination avoids generic solutions and allows interventions to be tailored to the real conditions of the context, creating a solid and sustainable working environment that endures beyond the project cycle.

Participation may be organised through an open call as well as targeted strategies to inform and engage key actors, including end-users of the activities and groups traditionally excluded.

In vulnerable neighbourhoods, the IN-HUB is configured as a polycentric, bottom-up, open, and flexible governance model, structured at three levels of involvement:

- **Steering group:** composed of residents and community organisations, it identifies needs and proposes solutions.
- **Operational level:** includes companies, institutions, and municipal bodies that assess the feasibility of proposals and provide knowledge and resources for their development.
- **Support level:** made up of partners, networks, and organisations that participate indirectly, contributing dissemination, endorsement, or occasional collaboration.

Coordination between these three levels supports project development and improves results. Constant interaction between the steering group and the operational level ensures that actions are viable, collaborative, and adapted to the context.

IN-HUB meetings can be held as often as needed, depending on requirements, and subcommittees can be set up for specific areas. While the full IN-HUB should ideally meet at least once a year, thematic or specific subcommittees may meet regularly as required.

BUILD INCLUSIVE GOVERNANCE

In Córdoba, for instance, numerous ad hoc meetings were organised to co-design, co-implement, and co-manage interventions together with relevant actors and residents.

The IN-HUB is a facilitating space for implementing the CO-CO-CO-CO methodology. Its design ensures that no single actor has unilateral control over decisions, fostering an environment of trust, negotiation, and collective learning.

In addition to guiding implementation, this platform contributes to the replicability of the model, integrating local knowledge, trust-based relationships, and multisectoral cooperation. Its functioning is open and adaptable, able to respond to new priorities, changing participation, or emerging dynamics, with the aim of becoming a lasting structure for future initiatives..

Methods:

- Inclusive actor mapping.
- Identification and outreach to key actors.
- Active and inclusive participation techniques.
- Tools adapted to participants' needs and capacities.
- Spaces for active listening and participatory dialogue.

Critical success factors:

1. Launch an open call to involve people interested in the project, while also contacting key actors directly, including those traditionally excluded.
2. Request commitment from those who wish to join the IN-HUB.
3. Avoid creating false expectations about project outcomes.
4. Start with a manageable number of committed partners.
5. Create subcommittees and define their roles clearly, while allowing them to evolve flexibly.
6. Provide opportunities for different actors to participate both in decision-making and in implementation.
7. Adapt working methods and tools to the needs and capacities of each level.

CO-DESIGN AN ACTION PLAN

DESIGN TANGIBLE AND INTANGIBLE (SOFT & HARD) INTERVENTIONS

The next step is to co-design an Inclusive Transformation Plan (ITP) to define the actions that will deliver the project results. This plan is developed in close collaboration with levels 1 and 2 of the IN-HUB, through a combination of bottom-up and top-down participatory processes. Participation is voluntary and does not include financial incentives.

The bottom-up approach is articulated through co-design workshops with residents, where participants collectively reflect on how they imagine their environment, what actions could be implemented, and which community resources could be mobilised. At this stage, the first level of the IN-HUB (made up of the local community) plays a central role. It is important that the resulting proposals are realistic and coherent with the objectives and resources of the project.

These initiatives are then reviewed in a top-down process with members of the second level of the IN-HUB, as well as with authorities, experts, and institutions, to assess their technical, economic, and institutional feasibility. Constant interaction between both levels makes it possible to adjust and refine the set of actions that will form the ITP.

IN-HABIT - Inclusive Health And wellbeing
In small and medium size cities

**D1.1. Inclusive
Transformation Plan
of Las Palmeras**

Cordoba's Pilot

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 869227

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14795145>

Methods:

- Inclusive actor mapping.
- Identification and outreach to key actors.
- Active and inclusive participation techniques.
- Tools adapted to the needs and capacities of participants.
- Spaces for active listening and participatory dialogue.

CO-DESIGN AN ACTION PLAN

The ITP should include all actions planned within the scope of the project, structured around the VIS (Visionary and Integrated Solutions). At the same time, it should remain a flexible and dynamic document, capable of adapting as the project evolves or as new community needs emerge.

Before implementing tangible VIS, it is important to develop social and cultural VIS that motivate, prepare, and connect residents, creating the conditions necessary for physical interventions to have both impact and acceptance.

- Tangible VIS include physical infrastructures, such as the refurbishment and renaturalisation of public spaces, the creation of picnic areas, community gardens, accessible pathways, or artistic murals, as well as digital tools (videos, platforms, sensors).
- Intangible VIS encompass social, cultural, or educational activities, such as cultural events, socio-cultural visits, wellbeing and healthy eating workshops, sports activities, or digital skills training, among others.

This dual approach ensures that spatial transformation is accompanied by real social activation, strengthening ownership and the long-term sustainability of interventions.

Critical success factors:

1. Co-design an action plan with all relevant actors, especially end-users or beneficiaries of the interventions.
2. Be realistic about the actions included in the ITP.
3. Ensure that actions can be implemented with the available human, financial, and institutional resources, and within the project's timeline.
4. Combine hard infrastructures with soft activities that make them viable and meaningful.
5. Recognise the fundamental value of intangible solutions as essential for the long-term impact of tangible ones, rather than as complementary.
6. Create flexible and dynamic plans that can adapt to changing contexts.
7. Design spaces to be used and lived in, not only to be seen.
8. Promote voluntary participation based on a genuine commitment to improving inclusive wellbeing in the neighbourhood, and not on monetary or similar incentives.

CO-IMPLEMENT THE ACTIONS

Once the ITP has been developed, actors must participate actively in its co-implementation and co-management. Participation is voluntary and no financial incentives are offered, although symbolic incentives are considered for those who remain continuously and meaningfully engaged throughout the process.

An initial analysis of existing skills helps to identify and make use of neighbourhood talents, ensuring they are made visible and recognised. It is advisable to begin with small-scale interventions to gauge their acceptance within the community before moving on to larger actions.

Although resident involvement is key, many interventions need to be subcontracted to specialised companies. In such cases, priority should be given to those that:

- Include people in vulnerable situations.
- Employ residents from the neighbourhood.
- Or demonstrate genuine social responsibility.

Providing training for the tasks to be carried out also helps to build local capacities and open up socio-economic opportunities.

Respecting local cultural practices facilitates community acceptance and participation, especially in diverse neighbourhoods. For example, in Córdoba, the Roma community celebrates night-time bonfires: setting up safe spaces and using fire-resistant materials makes it possible to integrate these traditions without creating risks or conflict.

The type of participation promoted by IN-HABIT empowers vulnerable groups, strengthens their sense of belonging, and fosters more sustainable use and maintenance of public spaces. To maintain coherence between the co-design process and the co-execution phase, it is essential to keep participants informed of any changes, challenges, or adjustments. This open communication helps to consolidate trust and commitment.

Methods:

- Co-responsibility workshops to foster collective commitment to change.
- Capacity-strengthening tools to equip individuals and groups with practical skills for implementing interventions and facing challenges.
- Educational training to promote long-term empowerment by increasing knowledge, confidence, and agency, enabling community members to participate actively and sustain transformation processes.
- Recognition and visibility activities to highlight achievements and acknowledge the actors who made them possible.
-

CO-IMPLEMENT THE ACTIONS

The sustainability of actions does not depend on their formal delivery once completed, but on the community's continuous involvement throughout the whole process, which ensures long-term ownership and maintenance.

It is also important to give visibility to what has been achieved, celebrating successes through inaugurations or cultural activities. These events are an excellent opportunity to highlight collective effort, reinforce community pride, and invite residents from other areas to learn about the changes promoted by the project. This contributes to improving the neighbourhood's image and building external links, even if it can be challenging in stigmatised contexts. Nonetheless, investing in such actions is worthwhile.

Critical success factors:

1. Identify existing talents and skills, and use and value them in co-implementation.
2. Build capacities and develop skills through practice and training (construction, planting, creative art).
3. Respect cultural traditions and practices when co-implementing interventions.
4. Start with small-scale interventions and evaluate residents' acceptance before moving to larger-scale actions.
5. Offer small but meaningful incentives to recognise participants (free access, public recognition, invitations to other decision-making spaces, or opportunities to present their results in wider contexts).

CO-MANAGE THE RESULTS

Once interventions have been implemented, their sustainability depends on the capacity for co-management and on how community involvement is articulated throughout the process. Sustainability is not achieved through handover strategies at the end of a project, but through the development of local capacities and community engagement from the very beginning.

This phase involves sharing responsibilities between residents, public administrations and, in some cases, the private sector, to ensure the maintenance and appropriate use of transformed spaces. Co-management should not be understood as a final step that begins only when results are visible but as a process that starts with co-design, reinforced during co-implementation and consolidates once results are tangible. Co-management is built in a way that allows the community to progressively engage and assume responsibilities.

Co-managing means that the spaces or actions created do not depend exclusively on institutions, but are embraced by the community as part of its daily life and local reality. This can take the form of neighbourhood management committees, cooperation agreements with local authorities, joint activities, and conflict-resolution mechanisms regarding the use of spaces and resources. Such collaborative and adaptive models respond better to the community's changing needs, ensuring that public spaces remain useful and relevant for their users.

Active involvement of residents reinforces the sense of belonging and can lead to stronger and more consistent participation in the daily management of spaces. In addition, limited institutional involvement in maintaining public spaces in vulnerable neighbourhoods may motivate residents themselves to take on a more active role, provided there is a sense of ownership and pride.

The experience of Córdoba demonstrates that when the community feels pride and ownership of what has been created, the risk of vandalism decreases, social cohesion is reinforced, and responsible use of public spaces increases. At the same time, institutions can find in the community an ally for ensuring maintenance, especially in neighbourhoods where public resources are limited or where complex social dynamics exist.

Co-management is not limited to distributing responsibilities or resolving potential conflicts; it also involves giving visibility to achievements and integrating them into collective, cultural, and social processes that take place at different times or under different circumstances. Celebrations, inaugurations, or cultural activities in the transformed spaces reinforce belonging, project a positive image, and attract more actors to the process. These dynamics strengthen the social and symbolic sustainability of the project just as much as the physical maintenance of the spaces.

Methods:

- Co-design processes and workshops that incorporate the dimension of co-management in their implementation and development.
- Community management committees, neighbourhood meetings, and local alliances.
- Collaboration agreements with local or regional authorities, associations, and NGOs for the maintenance of interventions.
- Mediation workshops on the use of spaces.
- Joint programming of cultural, social, and educational activities.
- Inaugurations, celebrations, and events that reinforce community pride.

Critical success factors:

1. Start co-management from the co-design phase, not at the end of the process.
2. Distribute responsibilities clearly but flexibly.
3. Guarantee minimum resources for maintenance.
4. Publicly recognise and value the efforts of residents and actors involved.
5. Ensure transparency in decision-making.
6. Promote diverse and inclusive use of spaces to avoid exclusive appropriation.

CO-EVALUATION AND MONITORING

Evaluation should be understood as a transversal thread running across all phases, not as an isolated exercise at the end of the process. It provides continuous feedback to adjust diagnosis, design, implementation, and management, ensuring a cycle of ongoing improvement. Evaluation should not be limited to checking whether objectives have been met or to what extent, but should instead become a participatory process of collective learning and continuous improvement.

IN-HABIT understands health and well-being holistically and shaped by the following dimensions and subdimensions:

Our co-evaluation framework makes it possible to understand what matters to the community and to assess not only the physical results of interventions, but also their impact on daily life, social cohesion, and people's subjective wellbeing. It also highlights options for improving co-creation, co-implementation, and co-management processes.

An effective system combines quantitative indicators (such as number of users, surface area recovered, reduction of emissions, or improvement in health indicators) with qualitative indicators that capture the community's perceptions, experiences, and narratives. This mixed-method approach ensures that technical data align with the lived reality of residents and reflect everyday circumstances.

Co-evaluation also has a temporal dimension. It is important to measure immediate impacts, which allow short-term corrections, while also establishing mechanisms for medium- and long-term follow-up and development perspectives.

Failures or initial difficulties should be understood as opportunities to learn, reflect, adjust, and improve. Flexibility and transparency in co-evaluation processes strengthen trust between institutions and the community, fostering commitment and involvement.

[Mac Fadden et al., \(2024\)](#)

CO-EVALUATION AND MONITORING

In Córdoba, among many other actions, citizen science tools have been used to monitor environmental parameters, alongside training and information sessions, weekly evaluation and discussion workshops, and regular meetings with residents to review progress. Creative formats have also been incorporated, such as evaluation through art, plastic expression, community photography, or music, allowing participants to express perceptions and emotions beyond formal questionnaires.

These formats encourage freedom of expression, remove potential barriers, and enable people with limited literacy or language barriers to contribute actively. Collective murals, theatre performances, and visual narratives have also been used to reflect how changes in the neighbourhood are perceived, creating a common language that transcends words and connects different generations.

Together, these dynamics have fostered a shared culture of co-evaluation in which residents are not merely informants but co-generators of knowledge, resources, and beneficiaries of their own actions.

Methods:

Participatory definition of quantitative and qualitative indicators.

Evaluation workshops with open dynamics and collective discussion.

Citizen science tools to involve the population.

Creative evaluation sessions (plastic arts, photography, music, theatre, visual narratives, etc.).

Collective murals and artistic representations to express personal and community perceptions and beliefs.

Use of accessible graphic and visual formats that overcome barriers of literacy or language.

Critical success factors:

1. Combine traditional methods with creative expressions that allow greater freedom and diversity in participation.
2. Ensure evaluation goes beyond closed responses, opening spaces for subjective and emotional expression.
3. Remove barriers by using graphic, artistic, and sensory resources.
4. Value not only technical results but also the stories, symbols, and collective representations generated by the community.
5. Promote a safe and trusting environment where everyone can express their views without feeling judged.
6. Strengthen the intergenerational dimension through art and culture as common languages that connect different groups.

06. METHODOLOGICAL ADAPTATION FRAMEWORK

This section presents the key elements of the proposed methodological framework for implementing inclusive health and wellbeing initiatives in vulnerable neighbourhoods, together with the common barriers that may arise when adapting it to other contexts.

Key elements:

- Create a steering group to drive the project, composed of authorities, researchers or facilitators, and a neighbourhood association.
 - Involve community activators with technical skills, contextual knowledge, and a high level of social commitment.
 - Establish an inclusive governance model representing the four key sectors: citizens, public sector, private sector, and academia.
 - Design adaptable projects with realistic timelines and resources.
 - Develop a thorough understanding of the local context and the history of previous interventions in the area.
 - Generate real opportunities for co-design, co-implementation, co-management, and co-evaluation with the community.
 - Practise active listening, especially with people who are most vulnerable or traditionally excluded.
- Combine tangible and intangible solutions to support both social transformation and the transformation of urban spaces, as well as the acceptance of physical actions.
 - Encourage the voluntary participation of residents who are genuinely interested in improving the inclusive health and wellbeing of their environment.
 - Apply robust scientific methods and generate useful evidence to inform decision-making and public policy.

Flexible elements:

- Projects and budgets may be limited, and actions small in scale. If the guidelines are followed, however, they can still achieve significant impact.
- Actions and solutions are highly variable and must be adapted to the environment, the population, and the specific objectives.
- The composition and internal dynamics of IN-HUBs may vary depending on the actors involved and their level of commitment.
- Evaluation methods should be adjusted to technological capacities, local needs, and available resources, but evaluation for adaptation and decision-making must always be an integral part of the process.

Barriers:

- Mistrust in institutions due to past failed experiences.
- Lack of social cohesion and a limited culture of collaboration among residents.
- Difficulties in identifying and involving key community profiles.
- Limited participation skills in vulnerable groups.
- Precarious living conditions (unemployment, poverty, daily urgencies) that hinder long-term commitment.
- General scepticism towards new initiatives.
- Lack of safe spaces and channels for community interaction.
- Projects and interventions with rigid, top-down designs that prevent adaptation and genuine participation.
- Shortages of human, technical, and financial resources.
- Dependence on political will, with the risk of discontinuity it entails.
- Prevalence of individualism over collective action.
- Environments with the presence of illegal activities, which create insecurity and hinder intervention..

REFERENCES:

- Badland, H., & Pearce, J. (2019). Neighbourhoods and health. Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198807157.001.0001>
- Carmichael, L., Barton, H., Gray, S., Lease, H., & Pilkington, P. (2017). Health-integrated planning at the local level in England: Impediments and opportunities. *Land Use Policy*, 66, 313–321. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2017.05.012>
- Corburn, J. (2017). Urban place and health equity: Critical issues and practices. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 14(2), 117. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph14020117>
- De Sá, T. H., Tainio, M., Goodman, A., Edwards, P., Haines, A., Gouveia, N., & Goldblatt, P. (2022). Health impact assessment of urban policies: A systematic review. *The Lancet Planetary Health*, 6(7), e606–e617. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196\(22\)00122-7](https://doi.org/10.1016/S2542-5196(22)00122-7)
- Kuddus, M. A., Tynan, E., & McBryde, E. (2020). Urbanization: A problem for the rich and the poor? *Public Health Reviews*, 41(1), 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40985-019-0116-0>
- Mac Fadden, I., Cocchioni, R. y Delgado-Serrano, M.M. (2024) «A Co-Created Assessment Framework to Measure Inclusive Health and Wellbeing in a Vulnerable Context in the South of Europe», *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 21(4), p. 510. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph21040510>
- McPhearson, T., Haase, D., Kabisch, N., & Gren, Å. (2016). Advancing understanding of the complex nature of urban systems. *Ecological Indicators*, 70, 566–573. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2016.02.059>
- Short, S. E., Mollborn, S., & Anderson, K. L. (2018). *The science of health disparities research*. Wiley. <https://doi.org/10.1002/9781119225722>

Follow us in our Social Media:

 @inhabith2020cordoba

@in_uco

 IN-HABIT H2020 UCO - CÓRDOBA

 @in_habit_uco

Check out this guide in

youtu.be/JZca-nrblwg

WANT TO KNOW MORE ABOUT IN-HABIT?

By scanning the QR code you can access the project's website, where you will find extended information about its objectives and activities. In the section dedicated to Córdoba, you will find practical resources and examples to implement Visionary and Integrated Solutions in your own context: from event maps to radio programmes, videos, and other support materials.

www.inhabit-h2020.eu

Through the Zenodo link you can access the project's repository, which gathers all generated data, publications, and documents. There you will find everything from scientific articles to technical reports and support materials, available for consultation and download.

www.zenodo.org/communities/in-habit-h2020/

On the project's YouTube channel you can see practical examples of the interventions carried out, with videos of presentations, workshop summaries, performances, and other activities that show the fieldwork and may serve as useful support tools.

www.youtube.com/@sustlabuco7791

UNIVERSIDAD
CÓRDOBA

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement No 869227